

Recommended citation: Virkki-Hatakka, T., Ikävalko, M., & Vuorio, A. (2021). Discipline matters or does it? Disciplinary differences in perceptions towards entrepreneurship. In Heiß, H.-U., Järvinen, H.-M., Mayer, A., & Schulz, A. (Eds.), *Blended Learning in Engineering Education: challengingm enlightening and lasting? SEFI 49th Annual Conference* (pp. 1520-1528). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Berlin, Germany. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14651560](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14651560).

DISCIPLINE MATTERS OR DOES IT? DISCIPLINARY DIFFERENCES IN PERCEPTIONS TOWARDS ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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Conference Key Areas: *Engineering education research, Capacity building*

Keywords: *Disciplinary difference, Attitudes, Entrepreneurship education, Competence development*

ABSTRACT

Entrepreneurship education (EE) is no longer limited to business school, but it has been introduced across campuses to different disciplines. The effects of EE on entrepreneurial attitudes have varied across studies, and discipline is one factor that has been suggested to play a role in student's disposition towards entrepreneurship, because culture and norms are also present in discipline-specific cultures, not just at the university level. This suggests that students from different disciplines tend to hold different dispositions towards entrepreneurship, which in turn has an impact on the effect that EE has on students. Thus, this research examines the question: do students start in different starting boxes in entrepreneurship courses.

The data consists of 218 students from multiple disciplines taking an online Introduction to Entrepreneurship -course in Finland via an online questionnaire. The results show that the average level of entrepreneurial intentions and attitude towards entrepreneurship differ between disciplines (engineering vs. non-engineering), having

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a business minor and gender. These results are further examined via fuzzy-set qualitative comparative analysis (fsQCA), which shows a difference in drivers of entrepreneurial intentions across disciplines, gender, and business minor. These results contribute to the EE literature by showing how different students start from different starting boxes in terms of perception of entrepreneurship, i.e. their disposition towards entrepreneurship differs across disciplines, minors, and gender. These results have implications for EE in the context of different disciplines by highlighting the contextuality of EE. The results also seem to suggest that it is worth exploring whether engineering students need specifically targeted entrepreneurship education, or more generally: should subjects suitable for many different fields be taught in a tailor-made way for students in different fields?

1 INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship education (EE) began in the field of economics, but recently it has also gained a foothold in the teaching of technical sciences. The effects of EE on entrepreneurial attitudes have varied across studies, and discipline is one factor that has been suggested to play a role in student's disposition towards entrepreneurship [1]. This is due to culture and norms, which are also present in discipline-specific cultures, not just at the university level [2]. Entrepreneurship education is defined as a specialized programme designed for developing awareness of the career options for entrepreneurs [3]. Regardless of the discipline, in the knowledge-intensive university context, knowledge taught and learned shapes the student's perceptions of what entrepreneurship includes and what entrepreneurship can offer for them. All this suggests that students from different disciplines tend to hold different dispositions towards entrepreneurship, and further, towards EE. The prior research has also shown that the effect that EE has on the change in student's entrepreneurial intention differs depending on a study major; the effect was larger among technology students than other students [4]. Surprisingly, although the prior research has shown that pre-educational entrepreneurial intentions and cultural, contextual, and personal variables [1] shape the outcomes of EE, there seems to be a lack of research focusing on the starting level of attitudinal factors towards entrepreneurship.

Based on the above, we propose that the connection between a discipline and the effectiveness of EE should be studied further. Keeping in mind that entrepreneurship has numerous real-life manifestations and assuming that EE is related to career planning, the strengths of students in different subjects may lead to different roles in entrepreneurship. This implies that students do not start entrepreneurship courses from the same starting points, but rather have different views towards entrepreneurship.

In this paper, we look for the differences that major subjects (engineering vs. other) bring to EE by utilizing the theory of planned behavior and causal complexity. First, the theory of planned behavior suggests that a person's behavior is a result of the combination of intention and perceived behavioral control [5]. Entrepreneurial intentions are shaped by three factors: attitude towards the behavior, social norms,

and perceived behavioral control. The higher the level of these three factors is, the more likely a person is to have a high level of entrepreneurial intentions. Second, causal complexity, on the other hand, proposes that different factors contribute to a presence of an outcome and these combinations of factors can differ [6]; [7]. This suggests that students from different disciplines may have different drivers for entrepreneurial intentions, thus highlighting the contextuality of EE. This theoretical background enables us to build on the prior literature, and address the following questions: do all students start their entrepreneurship study journey from the same starting box? If differences are found, what are the explanations?

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data collection

The data was collected using an online questionnaire as a part of a national-level web-based introductory course in entrepreneurship in Finland. These students represent several universities and multiple disciplines. The survey was sent to 290 students, who signed up for the course. Out of these students, 239 students responded to the questionnaire, and after removing incomplete responses and those denying the use of their data in research, 218 full responses were obtained (response rate of 75.2 %). The majority of the respondents (86.8 %) are under 35 years old. Female students account for 44.5 percent of the respondents (males 55.5 %). More than half (57.1 %) of the respondents have been studying in the university for three years or less. The majority of the respondents (76.4 %) have a family member, a relative or a friend who is an entrepreneur. However, only 7.7 percent currently belong to, or have been a member of a student entrepreneurship club, while 10.0 percent have work experience from a start-up and 15.5 percent have started a company.

2.2 Research methods

The measurement scales were adopted from the literature. Entrepreneurial intentions were measured via 7-point Likert scale developed by Liñan and Chen [8]. The scale consists of six items ranging from totally disagree to totally agree. Summated scale was formed based on the results of factor analysis (Cronbach's alpha=0.95). Similarly, perceived behavioral control and personal attitude were measured via a 7-point Likert scale adopted from Liñan and Chen [8]. The personal attitude scale ranges from strongly disagree to strongly agree, while the perceived behavioral control scale varies from completely agree to completely disagree. Summated scales were formed based on the results of factor analysis (Personal attitude: Cronbach's alpha=0.92, Perceived behavioral control: Cronbach's alpha=0.92). Social norms were measured via two scales reflecting the normative and descriptive nature of social norms. The normative social norms (Cronbach's alpha=0.81) were measured via a 7-point Likert scale adopted from Liñan and Chen [8], while the descriptive social norm (Cronbach's alpha=0.68) was adopted from the same scale by asking whether entrepreneurship is considered as an acceptable career option among family, friends and school mates.

Discipline was measured by asking the respondents what their major/discipline/field of study is with an open-ended question. This was then coded to respond to major fields of study, namely business, education, engineering, health sciences, arts and humanities, information technology, law studies, life sciences, physical sciences, and social sciences due to the imbalanced distribution of groups. For the analysis purposes, the measurement scale was dichotomized (1=engineering sciences, 0=non-engineering). Additionally, gender (0=female, 1=male) and business minor (0=no, 1=yes) were controlled for.

The data were analyzed via fuzzy-set qualitative comparative analysis (fsQCA). Fuzzy-set QCA focuses on an examination of causal complex relationships [6] by combining in-depth insights and generalizability, and the way an outcome is generated by the number of conditions [9]; [10]. Conditions refer to the input variables that are associated with the presence and/or absence of the outcome. In this paper, conditions include gender, discipline, minor, and the attitudinal drivers of entrepreneurial intentions, while the outcome is entrepreneurial intention. Fuzzy-set QCA bases on fuzzy logic, thus enabling an examination of degree in membership (fully-in, cross-over point, and fully out). The process of QCA is as follows: 1) dataset is calibrated (ranging between 0 and 1), 2) necessity and sufficiency of conditions are examined, 3) truth table is formed, and 4) systematic minimization is run to find configurations for a given outcome [11]. Following the recommendations of the prior literature, [12]; [11] the consistency threshold is set to 0.8, the proportional reduction in inconsistency (PRI) threshold is set to 0.6 and the minimum number of cases is defined as 2. Totally fuzzy and relative (TFR) calibration technique was used to accommodate the categorical nature of the data [13]. The results reported in this paper base on the intermediate solution, which utilizes logical reminders. To minimize the chance of untenable assumptions, contradictory simplifying assumptions were excluded from the minimization.

3 RESULTS

The results of the mean comparison show that the average level of entrepreneurial intentions and attitude towards entrepreneurship (ATB) differ between engineering science students and other students ($p < 0.1$). Additionally, having a business minor matters to the disposition towards entrepreneurship ($p < 0.05$; $p < 0.1$). Similarly, males have higher average entrepreneurial intentions and ATB than females ($p < 0.1$). This suggests that there seem to be attitudinal differences towards entrepreneurship.

To investigate this further, fsQCA was used in two steps. First, the necessity of conditions was examined. A necessary condition enables the existence of an outcome and has a consistency score equal or above 0.9 [6] and PRI equal to or above 0.6, and coverage of 0.6 [14]. The results of the fsQCA analysis show that there are five possible necessary configurations (See Table 1). To examine this further, a necessary condition analysis was run. The results show that ATB is the only single necessary condition for high entrepreneurial intentions (effect size = 0.22)

Table 1. Results of fsQCA analysis for high entrepreneurial intentions (outcome)

Necessary receipts										
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
~PBC + ATB	0.93	0.62	0.71							
PBC + ATB	0.94	0.63	0.72							
ATB + ~SNn	0.94	0.61	0.71							
ATB+~SNd	0.94	0.62	0.71							
Conditions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
ATB	●	●	●	●	●	●		●	●	●
PBC	●			○	●	●	●			●
normative SN	●			●				●	●	●
descriptive SN	●	●			●		●	●		
Engineering science		●	●	●	●	○	●		○	○
Business minor			○		●	○	○	○	●	○
Male			●	●		○	●	○	○	
Consistency	0.93	0.91	0.85	0.96	0.93	0.93	0.86	0.91	0.88	0.91
Coverage	0.46	0.30	0.20	0.21	0.13	0.15	0.12	0.16	0.05	0.20
Unique coverage	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.01
Solution consistency	0.88									
Solution coverage	0.76									

Notes: ~ denotes a negation of a condition (not high); ATB=attitude towards the behavior, PBC=perceived behavioral control, SN = social norms; black circle (●) denotes presence of a condition, white circle (○) denotes absence of a condition, empty space denotes that a condition is irrelevant for the receipt. Numbers on the top refer to each receipt (combination of conditions).

Second, the sufficiency of conditions was examined. The results show ten (1-10) distinct receipts that are associated with a high level of entrepreneurial intentions. These receipts differ in terms of drivers for entrepreneurial intentions as well as gender, discipline, and business minor. There is only one receipt (1), in which gender, discipline, and business minor do not play a role. In half of the receipts (2-5, 7), students are studying engineering sciences, while in three receipts (6,9,10) they are studying non-engineering fields. In most receipts, ATB is present, while only in one receipt (1) all four drivers of entrepreneurial intentions are present. Additionally, only in two receipts (1,8) both descriptive and normative social norms are present. Thus, the results highlight the multiplicity of factors and combination of factors shaping the level of entrepreneurial intentions. Based on the receipts, we propose two non-

discipline specific groups of students (entrepreneurially minded and acceptance seekers), five engineering-specific groups of students (acceptance seekers, entrepreneurially spirited, capability laggards, business experienced, and confident acceptance seekers), and three non-engineering specific groups of students (confidently entrepreneurially minded, experienced entrepreneurially spirited, and entrepreneurially minded). This suggests the need to take into account personal differences, when designing EE courses.

Next, the negative outcome, namely low (non-high) entrepreneurial intentions, was examined. The results in Table 2 show 11 distinct receipts that are associated with low entrepreneurial intentions. In most receipts, ATB is missing, and even through in three receipts (5,6,10) perceived behavioral control is present that does not help to overcome the lack of attraction towards entrepreneurship. Additionally, only in one receipt (10) both normative social norms and descriptive social norms are present; however, even these cannot compensate for the lack of attraction towards entrepreneurship (absence of ATB). All receipts differ in terms of gender, discipline, and business minor, thus highlighting the difference in students' backgrounds. Based on the receipts, we identified two non-discipline specific student group (convinced non-entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurial capability laggards), three engineering-specific student groups (capable non-entrepreneurs, non-entrepreneurially oriented, and accepted non-entrepreneurially oriented), and six non-engineering-specific student groups (non-entrepreneurs, not-accepted non-entrepreneurs, accepted capability laggards, conflicted capable, attitudinally influenced, and unwillingly capable).

Table 2. Results of fsQCA analysis for low entrepreneurial intentions (outcome)

Condition	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
ATB	○	○	○		○	○	○	○	○	○	○
PBC	○	○	○	○	●	●				●	○
nSN	○	○			●		○	○		●	
dSN			○	●	○	○	○		●	●	●
Engineering		○	○	○	○	●	○	●	●	○	
Business m.	○		○	●		●	○	●	●		○
Male	○	○		○	○			●	●	●	○
Consistency	0.93	0.94	0.92	0.96	0.90	0.94	0.93	0.94	0.88	0.91	0.93
Coverage	0.13	0.17	0.16	0.21	0.14	0.15	0.14	0.14	0.05	0.20	0.19
U. coverage	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.01
S consistency	0.89										
S coverage	0.66										

Notes: ATB=attitude towards the behavior, PBC=perceived behavioral control, nSN = normative social norms, dSN=descriptive social norms, business m.=business minor, U. consistency=unique

consistency, S consistency=solution consistency, S coverage=solution coverage; black circle (●) denotes presence of a condition, white circle (○) denotes absence of a condition, empty space denotes that a condition is irrelevant for the receipt. Numbers on the top refer to each receipt (combination of conditions).

4 SUMMARY

The results of the study suggest two issues. First, discipline, having a business minor, and gender with different combinations are present in 90 percent of receipts associated with high entrepreneurial intentions. Similarly, different combinations of discipline, gender, and having a business minor are present in all receipts associated with low entrepreneurial intentions. This is further reflected in the taxonomies: there are five engineering-specific taxonomies that are associated with high entrepreneurial intentions, while only three non-engineering-specific taxonomies are identified. Conversely, there are six non-engineering-specific taxonomies connected to low (non-high) entrepreneurial intentions, while only three are engineering-specific. This suggests that attention should be paid to the student's entrepreneurial background when designing an EE since these contextual factors seem to matter.

Second, it seems that high entrepreneurial intentions are more likely to be found among engineering students than among non-engineering students, while low entrepreneurial intentions are more likely to be found among non-engineering students rather than among engineering students. This seems to be partially explained by the difference in attitude towards entrepreneurship and perception in behavior control. Engineering students seem to perceive entrepreneurship as a more attractive career option than other students and they seem to believe they possess the skills and knowledge needed for entrepreneurship more than other students. Additionally, the absence of social norms in the case of low entrepreneurial intentions seems to add to the situation.

Based on these results, a taxonomy for student profiles can be formed, which enables contextualization of EE for non-discipline-specific, engineering-specific, and non-engineering-specific student groups. However, currently, EE seems to be one size fits all solution, although the results of this research seem to indicate differently. Similarly, recent research on entrepreneurial intentions has suggested a motivational difference [15], thus further highlighting the need to contextualize EE. These above-mentioned results seem to suggest that further studies are needed to clarify the phenomena behind variations in EI and further, the potential need for more targeted EE. The results suggest that it is worth exploring whether engineering students need specifically targeted entrepreneurship education. These findings raise some questions. Should subjects suitable for many different fields be taught in a tailor-made way for students in different fields? And further, would it be possible to develop a measurement tool based on the taxonomy developed in this study to find the optimal EE starting box for each student.

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Workshops

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